

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

The potential of circular fertilisers untapped - Opportunities and challenges ahead

18 Feb 2025 afternoon – 19 Feb 2025 morning
at [Silversquare Bailli](#) in Brussels

18 FEBRUARY 2025 – FULL AGENDA [HERE](#).

Keynote “The next institutional cycle (CAP) to boost the domestic production of circular fertilisers in the EU and to enable a sustainable and fair transition towards sustainable agriculture”.

Today's agriculture faces multiple challenges: environmental, social and economic. Circular fertilisers can support facing them by contributing towards soil health restoration, improved nutrient use efficiency and valorisation of biowaste streams. However, their uptake must overcome barriers, such as: lack of trust from farmers on their efficacy, lack of awareness on new technologies/products, high prices and need for more R&I investments. From a policy perspective, relevant ongoing and future initiatives will contribute to shaping the future of circular fertilisers, among others, by the future Common Agriculture Policy (CAP), the Vision for Agriculture and Food, the Water Resilience Strategy, the outcome of the Evaluation of the Nitrates Directive, as well as the European Commission's Working Programme 2025 mentioning the Clean Industrial Deal, and the Bioeconomy Strategy. Relevant recommendations are also included in the Strategic Dialogue for the Future of Agriculture. Slides from Mr. Stephanos Kirgagalis [here](#).

Session 1 “Environmental benefits and cost-competitiveness of circular fertilisers”.

Biowaste has an important role in the circular bioeconomy and in the production of biobased circular fertilisers, being compost and digestate the most produced and best-known. Circular fertilisers help to revert soil organic matter decrease and to increase carbon sequestration, but many potential end users may not trust their safety, quality or efficacy. Therefore, the creation of Voluntary Quality Assurance Schemes, as well as the improvement of biowaste streams quality, are essential to build trust with consumers and expand the market. Slides from Ms. Aline Granjard [here](#).

It is important to conceive and promote toxic free circular bio-products. In the specific case of some circular fertilisers, especially those obtained from animal manures, sewage sludge, wastewater, there are concerns for their content of pathogens, heavy metals, trace chemicals, drugs and other contaminants that can have a negative impact on our soils. Research projects should be oriented at unlocking the potential of circular fertilisers safeguarding safety, as well as effectiveness. Indeed, their macro- (NPK) and micro-nutrient profiles should be properly developed. Slides from Prof. Ľuboš Jurík [here](#).

Session 2 “Re-thinking LCA and LCC: enabling full accountability of the socio-economic benefits of circular fertilisers”.

Another way to foster trust in circular fertiliser is to deliver accurate evaluations of environmental, economic and social assessment of circular fertilisers. The most known endorsed methodologies for this purpose, namely Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC), fail in comprehensively modelling circular products and value chains and in accounting for all the positive effects of circular fertilisers. For example, the positive impact on soil is not considered, delivering misleading conclusions where conventional fertilisers seem to outperform circular ones. Also, environmental LCC results do not convey information about economic feasibility, but rather an aggregation of costs that may not be useful for decision-making processes. For the sake of circular fertiliser assessment, there is no one-size-fits-all - all assessment tools have blind spots – and the LCA/LCC must be integrated with other methodologies. Moreover, LCA/LCC practitioners need new indicators, emission factors, baseline and functional unit selection criteria. Slides from Mr. Hasler Iglesias [here](#).

NOVAFERT sister project aimed to develop a common method for the environmental assessment of circular fertilisers to demonstrate their environmental performance. They worked on mapping available LCA guidelines and standards, as well as other relevant environmental/sustainability criteria not well covered by traditional LCA methodologies (most related to the circular fertilisers application stage): affections on soil properties, soil carbon sequestration, heavy metals, biodiversity, microplastics, organic emerging contaminants, odour. Slides from Dr. Jorge Senán [here](#).

Session 3 “FER-PLAY recommends – flagship outcomes and considerations for the circular fertilisers community”.

FER-PLAY worked on collecting comprehensive data on tens of circular fertiliser value chains. Data referred to the production, storage and application stages, chemical-physical characteristics, cost and legislation. All of them are available on the [FER-PLAY database](#) and the user can filter data by fertiliser, feedstock type and geographical region. In a second phase, all identified value chains were evaluated with multiple criteria to select only seven (one per feedstock type) to be submitted to the [multi-assessment](#): the one described in the previous session, a regulatory assessment (see proceedings from the 19 Feb) and the assessment of industrialization potential. Moreover, FER-PLAY held 36 co-creation events to elaborate 3 sets of guidelines addressing [end-users](#), [producers](#) and [local administrations](#) to boost the market uptake of circular fertilisers. Main recommendations are: i) highly trained technical advisors for farmers are needed, ii) producers should improve their commercial strategies and iii) public administrations should develop circular bioeconomy strategies and act on the quality of waste, wastewater and by-products; more content in the linked documents. In addition, along the path to upscale from pilot to full-scale production, producers should consider the following: i) eventual legal constraints that can regionally affect the market; ii) guaranteeing product supply chain and constant and high quality of the fertiliser are a market pull; iii) start in niche markets to then expand potentially to the national level; iv) avoid cross-border hassle. Slides from Ms. Inès Verleden, Mr. Wim Moerman and Ms. Eva María López are available [here](#).

19 FEBRUARY 2025 – FULL AGENDA [HERE](#).

Keynote - R&D keys for market uptake of circular fertilisers.

Our food value chain is terribly inefficient: it requires high amounts of energy and nutrients, which production, logistics and application generate negative externalities on the environment. We need more efficient food production chains that avoid food loss, reduce emissions and increase nutrient recycling. The key of R&D success on nutrient recycling in Europe are: i) upscale of innovative technologies, ii) collaboration and knowledge sharing, iii) improvement of sustainability assessment, iv) get enough policy support and v) work on market acceptance of circular fertilisers and stakeholder engagement. Slides from Prof. Erik Meers [here](#).

Keynote – Diagnosis: regulatory barriers hindering the market uptake of circular fertilisers.

FER-PLAY assessed policies and legislations impacting production, application, marketing or promotion/financing of circular fertilisers by identifying barriers and proposing recommendations to move forward. Different pieces of legislation were considered. Regulatory drivers to enhance nutrient recycling and support the rollout of circular fertilisers are: i) revitalise the Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan, ii) implement target for Nutrients Recycling; iii) set up fiscal tools, iv) include agriculture into the ETS scheme and v) improve R&D. Slides from Ms. Lucile Sever [here](#), the full report on the regulatory analysis of FER-PLAY value chains can be downloaded [here](#).

Round-table to co-create policy recommendations for circular fertilisers market uptake.

Find the list of panellists [here](#) (side 1). The panellists discussed regulatory divers and challenges for the rollout of circular fertilisers. As per challenges, the most remarked ones are: i) a lack of knowledge of best practices across Europe, which widespread should be supported, ii) local authorities usually face staff shortage and budget limitations to implement the regulatory and policy frameworks; iii) the thresholds for contaminants should be reestablished based on scientific evidence, considering specific organic and inorganic forms (for example, organic As vs inorganic As) and specific farming scenarios; iv) more (brokered) interaction between EU research projects and policy makers at EU and local levels could lead to faster implementation of novel insights and technologies, while also more closely align with policy questions related to technological advances, opportunities and bottlenecks.

Roundtable “Circular fertilisers: what’s next to be done? – directions from R&D projects”

Find the list of panellists [here](#) (side 4). This session gathered the upcoming actions from R&D projects which are proposed to enhance market uptake of circular fertilisers. They are summarised as follows: i) Upscale of technologies: so far, RTOs participating in research projects are notable to produce the amounts that are needed for the industry and for field tests; ii) more aware-raising campaigns to increase the social acceptance; iii) develop B2C business models from a consortium of small-scale producers, because the distribution industry is not interested in small-medium volumes; the marketing strategy should ban the word “biowaste-derived”; iv) innovate to concentrate the nutrient contents and mix with conventional fertilisers to deliver a proper NPK balance; v) involve the fertiliser industry in the creation of formulations by blending circular and conventional fertilisers; vi) financial mechanisms like green bonds, should be introduced; vii) don’t lose the focus on feedstock pre-treatment: technologies for nutrient recovery have also the scope to control the pollution potential of wastewaters and efficiency is high when nutrients are very concentrated.

In addition, panellists added that traceability (of feedstocks and pollutants) is a key step to arise market trust. Emerging contaminants like microplastics are hindering the adoption of circular fertilisers for soil management practices.

Hybrid session for consumers, retailers, and local administrators – Circular Fertilisers: Chat on safety, benefits & market readiness?

This session aimed to introduce the role of circular fertilisers in sustainable agriculture, addressing their benefits, regulatory challenges, and market viability. Experts provided insights into the quality and safety, legal frameworks and market dynamics, followed by a discussion on the barriers and opportunities for their wider adoption.

Mr. Werner Vogt-Kaute (Naturland) highlighted the advantages of CFs, including improved soil health and resilience. However, strict quality standards are essential to maintain user trust, particularly regarding plastic contamination.

Ms. Vanesa Benito (GAIKER) provided an overview of EU regulations governing CFs, noting that while safety standards exist, there are gaps in setting clear limit values for environmental and human health risks.

Mr. Nicolas Scherrier (Brussels Environment) explained the complexities of composting regulations at different scales. Under the EU Animal By-Products (ABP) Regulation, sanitary requirements such as hygienisation (heating to 70°C for one hour) are necessary to achieve End-of-Waste (EoW) status, making small-scale composting nearly impossible under current rules. To address this, Brussels implemented its own regulation (BRUDALEX), allowing company and home composting under specific conditions. While companies are responsible for ensuring the quality of their compost, regional authorities focus on providing guidance through training, best practices, and occasional random quality tests rather than continuous monitoring. The adaptation of regulations was a bottom-up process, driven by existing practices. This model could be replicated in other regions now that a framework exists.

Ms. Morana Jednačak (IPS) discussed market challenges, including CFs’ smaller production scale, complex certification processes, and lack of regulatory harmonisation across EU member states. While CFs offer stable pricing compared to conventional fertilisers, they remain 20-30% more expensive on average. Farmers prioritise performance and safety over cost, emphasizing the need for education and demonstration of CF benefits.

Slides from Mr. Werner Vogt-Kaute, Ms. Vanesa Benito, Mr. Nicolas Scherrier and Ms. Morana Jednačak are available [here](#).

